

A NOTE ON THE CATALYTIC DECOMPOSITION OF NITROUS ACID

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Lungue (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1902, 18, 1) showed that aqueous solution of nitrous acid slowly passed into nitric acid and that different powders like sand, gypsum and charcoal accelerated the decomposition.

According to Taylor and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1882) the decomposition is at first rapid and and it subsequently slows down. It has also been shown that if nitrous acid is mixed with sodium sulphate under a layer of liquid paraffin, the decomposition is considerably retarded. Dhar (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 3, 255) showed that the decomposition of nitrous acid into nitric acid and nitric oxide was retarded by mild reducing agents and accelerated by the oxidising agents. All these workers have studied the catalytic decomposition of this acid by estimating it volumetrically (Valey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 413).

In the present investigation the catalytic decomposition has been followed by colorimetric analysis which is considered to be far more sensitive than volumetric methods. Nitrous acid, prepared by the action of dilute hydrochloric acid on silver nitrite along with 1 g. of catalyst, was allowed to attain the temperature of the experiment. After regular intervals of time a known volume of the nitrous acid solution was withdrawn and estimated colorimetrically by Griess Ilosova's reagent (sulphanilic acid and α -naphthylamine).

TABLE I
Percentage of decomposition.

Time.	Catalyst.					
	None.	Am. persulph.	Phthalic anhydride.	Pot. oxalate.	Liq. paraffin.	Molybdic acid.
0 hr.	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	14.8	27.3	—	—	—	—
1.0	27.3	48.5	15.3	—	4.6	—
2.0	45.5	75.2	27.3	3.10	8.0	—
4.0	69.4	97.0	50.0	6.10	—	1.5
7.5	88.70	—	—	—	—	—
8.0	—	—	78.8	10.60	20.50*	—
24	—	—	—	27.30	43.2	10.7
48	—	—	—	42.50	68.2	18.2
60	—	—	—	—	77.3	—
80	—	—	—	—	89.8	—
120	—	—	—	59.10	—	37.9
240	—	—	—	—	—	60.7
384	—	—	—	92.50	—	80.3
480	—	—	—	—	—	89.4

It has been observed by the authors that ammonium persulphate acts as a positive catalyst whereas phthalic anhydride, potassium oxalate, molybdic acid and liquid paraffin act as negative catalysts. The qualitative differences in the behaviour of these catalysts are indicated in the table.

In case of salts like potassium nitrate and sodium sulphate, it has been observed that they have got no catalytic effect.

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